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How to read English words correctly

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Abstract: The article contains recommendations on how to speak English correctly.

Key words: English, word, pronunciation, reading, sound, letters, conversation.

A person who begins to learn a foreign language, first of all, faces the problem of reading and pronouncing English words. Even many native speakers have trouble reading correctly, and as such, it becomes a barrier for language learners. But, nevertheless, it is very important to be able to read and pronounce the text correctly in the target language, as well as to know and correctly apply the rules of pronunciation.

To learn to read English from scratch, it is important to learn the English alphabet first. It consists of 26 letters (6 vowels, 20 consonants).

Beginners should learn the correct pronunciation of all sounds, because English is different from Russian (but there are similarities). To pronounce correctly, you need to train your mouth and pronounce.

After establishing the pronunciation of sounds, it is necessary to learn the basic rules of reading vowels and consonants. Transcription during reading can be in English or Russian. Use dictionaries for reading comprehension, not online

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translators

Why is it difficult to study in English?

For example:

Some letter combinations are pronounced as one sound.

In Russian, a soft sign is used to soften the sound, in English there is no such sign. Instead, the transcription shows the position of the letter in the word or symbol.

In fact, English is much easier than Russian, because there are no cases or declensions, and it is not difficult to speak it (if you practice). The difficulty arises due to the fact that the pronunciation of the familiar native language is different from the learned one.

English pronunciation and English sounds

The pronunciation and sounds of the English language are directly related to their transcription (recording the sound of certain letters or words). In turn, transcription depends on the rules of reading.

In English:

44 sounds;

20 voice sounds;

24 consonants.

English pronunciation of native speakers is also divided into several parts. It depends on the origin of the carrier. For example, American pronunciation is different from English. And this is expressed not only in the accent, but also in the pronunciation of the same words or sounds. Nowadays, American pronunciation is more relevant because most students speak it.

Language position

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One of the features of the pronunciation of English words is the position of the tongue. Therefore, problems may arise during reading, because the position of the tongue should be the same when pronouncing Russian letters, and it should be different when pronouncing similar English letters.

Articulation power

Articulation is also important in reading English. With proper articulation, first of all, your mouth and, basically, the entire speech apparatus will be in a tense state, and the conversation will be tiring for some time. All this is due to lack of preparation and lack of habit, because in Russian the vocal apparatus is in a relaxed state.

For native speakers, this articulation does not cause discomfort, because their mouth is in a normal position. But they have trouble pronouncing Russian letters and words. Again, everything is normal.

Rules for reading words

It is very important to learn English reading rules. There is a significant difference between the spelling and pronunciation of English letters, words and phrases.

There are a few basic rules to keep in mind when reading:

The rule of open and closed joints. There is no such rule in Russian. An open syllable is a syllable that ends with a vowel sound. It can appear in several cases: - the word ends with a vowel (lake - lake); - in a word, two vowels stand in a row (cruel - cruel); - there is a consonant between two vowels in the word (education - education).

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Rules for pronouncing consonants and vowels. For this, it is worth familiarizing yourself with the transcription table.

Diphthong and triphon rule. This is the rule of combining 2 or 3 letters that have a certain sound.

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How to read consonants?

Many consonants in the English language do not differ much from the pronunciation of consonants in the Russian language, but there is a difference.

There are a few special features to note. It should be remembered that all English consonants are pronounced only hard, and voiced consonants at the end of words are not pronounced as boring.

Also, the pronunciation of individual sounds has the following features:

The pronunciation of V sound is different from V. The sound (V) should be spoken with both lips, and (V) with only the lower lip.

P, T, K sounds - pronounced with a further aspiration.

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About half of the sounds should be pronounced with the tongue touching the upper palate.

How to pronounce vowels: 4 different syllables

There are also specific rules for reading vowel sounds. There are 4 main types of reading sounds in English (E, A, Y, U, O, I). The pronunciation of the sound in a word or phrase depends on each species.

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